

PHOSPHORUS-CONTAINING FLAME RETARDANT RAMIE FIBER REINFORCED POLY(LACTIC ACID)(PLA) COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The composites made by biodegradable natural fibers and biodegradable polymers have raised great attention due to their acceptable mechanical properties and environmental benefits such as biodegradability, less greenhouse gas emissions, and renewability[1,2]. Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), a biodegradable thermoplastic polymer with high strength and modulus, has been is a perfect eco-material for many studies during the past decade for its potential in renewable engineering materials. PLA provides good aesthetics and easy processability in most equipment. In processing and manufacturing, the price and inherent brittleness are the most limitation for its wide practical applications. [3, 4] Natural fibers were obtained from the leaves or the stems of the plants. As a naturally growing material, they possess low price, low density, high specific strength and modulus, no health risks, easy availability in some countries and environmental friendly [5, 6]. The composites made by natural fibers and PLA have been used for making automotive parts, building components, and aircraft interior parts due to their acceptable mechanical properties, biodegradability and renewability[7]. For these applications flammability performances are highly required, improvement of flammability properties of these biocomposites becomes more and more important.

In the past decade, several methods have been applied for the synthesis of flame-retardant

biocomposites [8,9]. Low cost, low-toxicity and high efficiency are the development directions for flame-retardant biocomposites. Traditionally, brominated compounds and antimony oxide are used to improve the flammability of the polymer. Considering that the generation of toxic, corrosive, and halogenated gases and the release of toxic, endocrine-disrupting chemicals in combustion should be avoided, the halogen-free products, phosphorus, silicon, and nitrogen compounds, are mostly used to replace brominated compounds in flame retarding polymer.[10]

Ammonium polyphosphate (APP) is a very common and popular inorganic phosphorus/nitrogen flame retardant, which usually demonstrates a significant phosphorus-nitrogen synergism. Literature has suggested various physical modes of flame-retardant action of APP, such as the formation of polyphosphoric acid as a surface coating, the heat sink action of the vaporizing phosphorus compound, dilution of the combustible pyrolysates by a less combustible vapors, and reduction of melt viscosity that favor a melt drip mode of flame extinction[11]. According to Wang et al[12], only 5 wt% of APP can increase the LOI value of epoxy resins from 19.6 to 27.1, and improve the UL-94 ratings, reaching V-0 rating from no rating.

9,10-Dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide(DOPO) is a type of cyclic phosphate with a diphenyl structure, which has high thermal stability, good

oxidation resistance, and good water resistance. DOPO shows excellent flame-retarding properties in the materials. Thereby DOPO can either act only in the gas phase by flame inhibition, or in the gas phase and in the condensed phase (by char formation) at the same time [13, 14].

In the present study, APP and DOPO were used to impart flame retardancy to ramie/PLA biocomposites respectively. The flammability of the composites was deeply investigated by UL94, LOI and SEM measurement. The influence of APP and DOPO on the mechanical properties of the biocomposites was also studied.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) (NatureWorks® 4032D, having T_g of 52-58°C, T_m of 150°C and M_w of 140,000) was purchased by NatureWorks Co. Ltd.. Ramie yarn was supplied by Shanghai Qian-Cong Ramie Products Co. Ltd. (China). Ammonium polyphosphate (APP) ($M_n > 1000$) was obtained from Shanghai Xunshen Flame Retardant Co. Ltd (China). DOPO, commercial grade, from the Huizhou Sunstar Technology Co. Ltd., China, was dried at 100°C for 2 hours before use since a certain amount of hydrated DOPO is usually found in the reagent (Shown in Fig.1).

Fig. 1 Hydrolysis reaction of DOPO

2.2 Preparation of the composites

PLA, ramie yarn, APP and DOPO were dried at 50°C in vacuum for 10h, respectively. Then the dried PLA and APP (or DOPO) were firstly well mixed. The obtained mixture and ramie yarn were blended in a co-rotating twin-screw

extruder (F:20mm, L/D:40, Jieya: Nanjing, China) at operating temperature from 155 to 175 °C. The extrudate was quenched in a water bath, cut into pellets and then dried in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 8h. The compositions are shown in Table 1. The biocomposites obtained were then molded into sheets by hot pressing at 170°C and 20 MPa for 4 min, followed by cooling to room temperature at 5Mpa. The sheets were prepared for structure characterization and properties measurements.

Table 1 Compositions of different materials

Specimens	PLA	Ramie	APP	DOPO
	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)
Ramie/PLA	90	10	-	-
Ramie/PLA/10 APP	80	10	10	-
Ramie/PLA/10 DOPO	80	10	-	10

2.3 Characterization

LOI measurements and UL94 vertical burning test were used to evaluate the flame retardancy of the specimens. LOI values were determined by an HC-3 LOI instrument (Nanjing Fangfen Analytical Instrument Factory, China) according to GB 2406-1996 standard (China) with the dimension of 70mm×6.5mm×3mm. UL94 testing were performed by using a WC-5400 vertical burning test instrument (Kunshan Vouch Testing Instrument Factory, China) according ASTM D-3801 standard with the dimension of 125mm×13×3mm³.

TGA was employed to analyze the thermal stability of the untreated and treated composites. Scans were carried out at a heating rate of 10°C/min in inert nitrogen atmosphere (80ml/min)

from ambient to 600°C, by using a STA 449C thermogravimetric analyzer (NETZSCH, Germany).

The morphologies of the impact fractured surfaces of the composites were observed and analyzed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Quanta 200 FEG, FEI Company) at room temperature. The samples were coated with gold using a vacuum sputter coater. The samples were viewed perpendicular to the fractured surface.

Specimens of the composites were tested for tensile strength according to GB 13022-91 standard using a CMT5105 Materials Testing Machine (Shenzhen Sansi Material Instruments Ltd., China). The composites were tested for flexural strength under three point bending in a DXLL-5000 machine (Shanghai Jiedeng Instruments Ltd., China) in accordance with GB 1449-83.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 LOI test

LOI and UL-94 tests are effective methods in evaluating the flame retardancy, and have become the main criterion in polymer industry. The LOI is defined as the minimum fraction of O₂ in a mixture of O₂ and N₂ that will just support flaming combustion. Generally, when LOI value greater than 26, materials can be considered to have flame retardancy[15]. The results of LOI test were shown in Table 2. PLA and ramie fiber are flammable materials, thus ramie/PLA composite is completely consumed. The LOI value of Ramie/PLA is only 21.6%. At the same time, it is observed that LOI values obviously leveled up from 21.6% to 26.8% and 28.3% respectively, when APP and DOPO were incorporated respectively. These facts indicate that APP and DOPO impart the composites a certain of flame retardancy. The LOI values of the composites with DOPO loading is high than that of the composites with APP loading. The specimens after LOI tests are shown in Fig.2. It

is observed that the composites with APP and DOPO could generate char.

Table 2 LOI values of the composites

Specimens	LOI (%)
Ramie/PLA	21.6
Ramie/PLA/10APP	26.8
Ramie/PLA/10DOPO	28.3

Fig.2 Specimens after LOI test,

A: Ramie/PLA/10APP, B: Ramie/PLA/10DOPO

3.2 UL-94 measurement

Table 3 Flame retardancy of the composites

Specimens	t ₁ (s)	t ₂ (s)	UL-94	Dripping
Ramie/PLA	>30	-	NR	Yes
Ramie/PLA/10APP	2	8	V-0	Yes
Ramie/PLA/10DOPO	1	3	V-0	Yes

The results of UL-94 measurements are shown in Table 3. Ramie/PLA did not pass the UL-94 test for no self-extinguish, and had serious melt dripping at the first and second flame application. The dripping from specimens could ignite the cotton. The composites with APP and DOPO loading had very short combustion time and lighter melt dripping on the first and second flame application. The melt dripping did not ignite the cotton, and the composites could reach V-0 rating. When cooperating with APP and DOPO, ramie fiber being rich in polyhydric compound acts as a charring agent to form a

Fig.3 Specimens after UL 94 measurement, A: Ramie/PLA/10APP, B: Ramie/PLA/10DOPO

intumescent flame retardant system. Generally, when exposed high temperature, phosphorus-containing flame retardant would release phosphoric acid, polyphosphoric acid and non-flammable gases. The resulting acid is contributed to ramie dehydrating intramolecularly or intermolecular, then dehydrogenizing, charring and rupture of chemical bonds. The phosphorus results in flame inhibition through radical trapping in the gaseous phase, and the non-flammable gases

can dilute the fuel concentration in flame and thus weaken or quench the flame. This physical and chemical contribution in both condensed phase and gas phase play an important role in flame retardancy[16]. From Fig.3, it is observed that the composites with APP loading after burning test could keep shape relative intact. It shows that the melt dripping of ramie/PLA/10APP is lighter than that of ramie/PLA/10DOPO.

3.3 TGA

The thermal stability of the ramie/PLA composite with different flame retardant was investigated by TGA, and the results are presented in Fig. 4. Thermal degradation of ramie/PLA shows completely in a single stage and occurs at 335.1 °C . The T_{onset} of ramie/PLA/10DOPO is similar to that of ramie/PLA. It shows that the improvement of thermal stability of the composites can be negligible with the addition of DOPO. However, the T_{onset} of ramie/PLA/10APP is lower which is due to the DOPO loading. APP starts decomposing around 215°C to release gas of

Fig.4 TGA curve of the composites with different flame retardant

Fig. 5 SEM Micrographs of the composites with different flame retardant
A: Ramie/PLA, B: Ramie/PLA/10APP, C: Ramie/PLA/10DOPO

NH_3 and H_2O , and from 500°C to 700°C , APP release phosphoric acid, poly-phosphoric acid leaving 19% weight[17]. When the temperature increase above 400°C , the matrix and the flame retardant begins to fully develop a bonded char structure. During the char formation, the heat and the amount of burning the volatile products are drastically reduced, and thermally stable char in high temperature is contribute to the thermal and flame protection to matrix. Moreover, it can be observed that the residue left at 600°C increases significantly as the addition of APP and DOPO. The results can explain the improvement of flame retardancy of the composites.

3.4 Morphology analysis

SEM micrographs of the impact fracture surfaces of the composites are represented in Fig.5. As shown in Fig.5(a), the ramie fibers disperse in the form of a

separated fiber. From Fig.5(b) and (c), the APP and DOPO are well dispersed in the PLA/ramie composites respectively. No large agglomerates of the APP and DOPO and good adhesion between the matrix and the flame retardant are observed, which should play an important role in improving the flame retardancy discussed above. APP and DOPO adsorbed on the surface of ramie fibers or blended in PLA matrix has an influence on the interface between and ramie fibers. From Fig.5 (b) and (c), it can be seen that there are obvious voids between the fibers and PLA. These phenomena indicate that the interfacial adhesion is weak between PLA and nature fibers.

3.5 Mechanical properties

The addition of flame retardant would weaken the adhesion between fiber and matrix, so it is necessary to study the influence of phosphorus-containing flame retardant loading on the mechanical properties of the biocomposites. To develop a flame retardant

Fig. 6 Tensile properties of the composites with different flame retardant

biocomposite maintained its level of mechanical performance is a big challenge. It is well known that mechanical performance of composites is dependent

on the properties of the materials comprising the composite and their combined process. The composites with different flame retardant

Fig. 7 Flexural properties of the composites with different flame retardant

loading were further evaluated by tensile and flexural testing. Data pertaining to the tensile properties are shown in Fig.6. It can be seen that the tensile strength and tensile modulus of ramie/PLA composite were 42.65MPa and 4.31GPa respectively. The tensile strength and tensile modulus have sharply decreased with the addition of APP and DOPO. For example, after adding DOPO, the tensile strength and tensile modulus decreased to 33.81MPa and 3.98GPa respectively.

Fig.7 shows the flexural properties of the composites with different flame retardant. It is similar with the tensile properties that the flexural strength and flexural modulus of the composites sharply decrease with the addition of APP and DOPO. When adding DOPO to the composites, the flexural strength and flexural modulus decreased from 88.87.23MPa to 62.55MPa and 4.24GPa to 3.84GPa respectively. This may be due to the fact that high loading of the flame retardant influences the interface bonding between PLA matrix and ramie fibers. The compatibility between fibers and PLA becomes poor. It is well known that the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced polymer composites are greatly influenced by the interfacial bond strength. The compatibility between the polymer matrix and the ramie fibers is worsened by hindering interaction at the polymer/fibers interface. Well interfacial adhesion between ramie and PLA can increase the amount of energy required for pulling it out, the mechanical properties of the ramie/PLA composite with well interfacial adhesion are higher than that of the PLA composite with poor adhesion [18]. Based on these results, it is apparent that the addition of the flame retardant to the ramie fibers reinforced PLA composites decreases the mechanical properties of the composites.

4. Conclusion

1) Ramie reinforced PLA biocomposites with phosphate containing flame retardant loading were prepared by using twin-screw extruder. The flammability and mechanical properties of ramie/PLA composites were studied. The composite can achieve UL-94 V-0 rating with the addition of APP and DOPO. According to TGA results, both APP and DOPO can effectively increase char

residue at high temperature, resulting the improvement of flame retardancy.

2) It can be directly observed from SEM image that the two kinds of flame retardant introduced into the composites disturbs the compatibility between PLA and ramie fibers. Flame retardant will decrease the mechanical properties of the composites.

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References

- [1] M Smita, K. Sushil and K. Sanjay "Dynamic mechanical and thermal properties of MAPE treated jute/HDPE composites". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 66, pp538-547, 2006.
- [2] D Ray, B Sarkar, A Rana and N Bose "The mechanical properties of vinylester resin matrix composites reinforced with alkali-treated jute fibers". *Compos Part A*, Vol. 32, pp119-127, 2001.
- [3] L Yu, D Katherine and L. Lin "Polymer blends and composites from renewable resources" *Prog Polym Sci*, Vol 31, pp576-602, 2006.
- [4] J Ren, T Yu, H Li, T Ren and S Yang "Studies on morphologies and thermal properties of poly(lactic acid)/polycaprolactone/organic-modified montmorillonite nanocomposites". *Polym Compos*, Vol. 29, pp1145-1151, 2008.
- [5] S Masud, T Lawrence, K Amar and M Manjusri "Chopped glass and recycled newspaper as reinforcement fibers in injection molded poly(lactic acid) (PLA) composites: A comparative study". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol 66, pp1813-1824, 2006.
- [6] T Yu, Y Li and J Ren "Preparation and properties of short natural fiber reinforced poly(lactic acid) composites". *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*, Vol. 19, pp S651-S655, 2009.
- [7] T Yu, J Ren, S Li, H Yuan and Y Li "Effect of fiber surface-treatments on the properties of poly(lactic acid)/ramie composites". *Composites: Part A*, Vol 41, pp 499-505, 2010.
- [8] Z Wu, W Xu, Y Liu, J Xia, Q Wu and W Xu "Preparation and characterization of flame-retardant

- melamine cyanurate/polyamide 6 nanocomposites by in situ polymerization". *J App Polym Sci*, Vol 113, pp 2109-2116, 2009.
- [9] G Jenny and M Shlomo "Synthesis and characterization of new flame-retardant microspheres by dispersion polymerization of pentabromobenzyl acrylate". *European Polymer Journal*, Vol 45, pp 2987-2995, 2009.
- [10] S Lu and I Hamerton "Recent developments in the chemistry of halogen-free flame retardant polymers". *Prog Polym Sci*, Vol 27, pp 1661-1712, 2002.
- [11] L Chen and Y Wang "A review on flame retardant technology in China. Part I: development of flame retardants". *Polym Adv Technol*, Vol 21, pp 1-26, 2010.
- [12] J Wang, D Wang, Y Liu, X Ge and Y Wang "Polyamide-enhanced flame retardancy of ammonium polyphosphate on epoxy resin". *J App Polym Sci*, Vol 108, pp 2644-2653, 2008.
- [13] B Perret, B Schartel, K Stob, M Ciesielski, J Diederichs, M Doring, J Kramer and V Altstadt "Novel DOPO-based flame retardants in high-performance carbon fibre epoxy composites for aviation". *European Polymer Journal*, Vol 47, pp 1081-1089, 2011.
- [14] X Chen, A Gu, G Liang, L Yuan, D Zhuo and J HU "Novel low phosphorus-content bismaleimide resin system with outstanding flame retardancy and low dielectric loss". *Polym Degra Stab*, Vol 97, pp 698-706, 2012.
- [15] S Li, H Yuan, T Yu, W Yuan and J Ren "Flame-retardancy and anti-dripping effects of intumescent flame retardant incorporating montmorillonite on poly(lactic acid)". *Polym Adv Tech*, Vol. 20, pp. 1114-1120, 2009.
- [16] S Duquesne, R Delobel, M Bras and G Camino "A comparative study of the mechanism of action of ammonium polyphosphate and expandable graphite in polyurethane". *Polym Degra Stab*, Vol 77, pp 333-344, 2002.
- [17] S Li, J Ren, H Yuan, T Yu and W Yuan "Influence of Ammonium polyphosphate on the flame retardancy of ramie fiber reinforced poly(lactic acid) biocomposites". *Polym Int*, Vol 59, pp 242-248, 2010.
- [18] D Chen, J Li and J Ren "Combustion properties and transference behavior of ultrafine microencapsulated ammonium polyphosphate in ramie fabric-reinforced poly(L-lactic acid) biocomposites". *Polym Int*, Vol 60, pp 599-606, 2011